

Potassium Hexaisothiocyanatoferrate(II)hexapyridyl-molybdenum(III) and related Complexes

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Bimetallic hexathiocyanate complexes of the type, $K[Fe(NCS)_6][Mo(L)_n]$ ($n = 6$ when $L = py$ or nia , $n = 3$ when $L = bipy$ or $phen$) have been prepared and characterised. All the complexes are ionic and thiocyanate groups are bonded to Fe^{II} through nitrogen-end. In all the complexes molybdenum is in octahedral environment. The proposed structures have been supported by HSAB principle and softness parameters. The complexes show enhanced fungitoxicity towards some soil fungi.

The role of essential trace elements in biological systems is gaining momentum exponentially¹. In various heme derivatives the role of iron is clear, there are many instances in which the function of this trace metal² is known. Molybdenum and iron both play important role in the nitrogen cycle as these metals have been proved as important constituent of nitrogenase enzymes³. Mo and Fe also behave as moderately toxic metals⁴ the reason not yet known. It seems more probable that mixed metal thiocyanate complexes of Mo and Fe may be more toxic as the mixed metal thiocyanate complexes of Mo with other transitional metals, e.g. Cu or Ag have been found more toxic towards soil fungi⁵.

The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of bimetallic mixed metal thiocyanate complexes of the type $K[Fe(NCS)_6][Mo(L)_n]$ ($n = 6$ when $L = py$ or nia , $n = 3$ when $L = bipy$ or $phen$) a new family of bimetallic mixed metal thiocyanate complexes. The application of these complexes in the soil as fungicide may give fruitful results.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) confirm general formula $K[Fe(NCS)_6][Mo(L)_n]$ ($n = 6$ when $L = py$ or nia , $n = 3$ when $L = bipy$ or $phen$) for these complexes. Molar conductance values of all the complexes have been found in the range $164-189 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$, indicate that they are 2-1 electrolyte⁶. They decompose in the temperature range $120-260^\circ$. Magnetic moment values lie in the range $3.60-3.69 B.M.$ showing their paramagnetic character equivalent to three unpaired electrons.

In the electronic spectra, two main bands at $25960-24600$ and $33920-31960 cm^{-1}$ have been assigned to the transitions, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(v_1)$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(v_2)$, for octahedral molybdenum(III) complexes. The correct location of third spin allowed transition ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(v_3)$, becomes possible due to the presence of charge transfer or ligand bands in the same region. By inserting the appropriate Tanabe-Sugano⁷ secular equation of d^3 -system, we have also calculated Racah's electronic repulsion parameter (β) whose values (Table 1) have been found to be closer to octahedral Mo^{III} complexes reported earlier⁵.

One to two bands in the IR spectra of these complexes in the range $2080-2000 cm^{-1}(CN)$ indicate the presence of only N-bonded terminal thiocyanate groups. One to three bands observed for ν_{C-N} and δ_{Fe-C-N} at $850-770$ and $490-460 cm^{-1}$ respectively confirm the presence of only N-bonded terminal thiocyanates. Comparison of the spectra of the ligand and the complexes, reveals positive shift in ν_{C-N} bands due to ring vibrations, showing the involvement of ring nitrogen in the coordination^{9,10}. Further, the presence of a band at $280-260 cm^{-1}$ ($Mo-L$) indicates the coordination of ligand to Mo^{III} ⁵.

The results show that Mo in these complexes is in octahedral field. Hence, we suggest that the complexes are cationic-anionic type in which Mo^{III} with ligands forms the cation and the Fe^{II} with six thiocyanates forms the anion. It indicates cationic-anionic structure of these complexes.

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL, ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND SPECTRAL PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd (Colour, Decomp temp °C)	Analysis % Found/(Calcd)				λ_{max} cm ⁻¹	<i>Dq</i>	<i>B</i>
	Mo	Fe	S	N			
K[Fe(NCS) ₆][Mo(py) ₆] (Brown, 125)	9.9 (9.5)	5.7 (5.6)	19.2 (18.9)	15.1 (16.6)	11 200, 9 200 (18 000, 24 000, C T bands)	2 460	686
K[Fe(NCS) ₆][Mo(mia) ₆] (Brown, 120)	8.4 (7.6)	4.5 (4.4)	16.1 (15.1)	18.2 (19.8)	11 300, 9 100 (18 205, 23 800 C T bands)	2 520	697
K[Fe(NCS) ₆][Mo(bipy) ₃] (Red, 220)	10.4 (9.5)	5.6 (5.6)	18.9 (19.1)	14.8 (16.7)	11 350, 9 050 (18 200, 23 905, C T bands)	2 592	741
K[Fe(NCS) ₆][Mo(phen) ₃] (Red, 260)	9.9 (8.5)	4.9 (4.9)	17.8 (16.9)	12.8 (14.8)	11 250, 9 110 (18 050, 23 900, C T bands)	2 596	745

These structures have also been supported by following facts. The ν_{Fe-NCS} band at 298–293 cm⁻¹ supports the presence of only N-bonded thiocyanate groups¹¹. The *Dq* values of the complexes are quite higher than those of the isothiocyanate complexes, but in the range already prescribed for Mo^{III}N₆(L) chromophore^{8, 12}, which favours the coordination of ligand molecules with molybdenum. HSAB principle¹³ and quantitative softness calculations discussed below also support the coordination of ligand molecules with Mo^{III}.

The softness values of various ligands and metals have been calculated by using Klopman's equations^{6, 14}. The results are presented in Table 2. A higher value of $E_n^\ddagger$ for Lewis acid and lower values of $E_m^\ddagger$ for Lewis base indicate greater softness. As a result the softness of Lewis acid and base increases in reverse direction. Hence, a better match of soft-soft and hard-hard interactions will be obtained by higher value of softness difference ($\Delta E_{nm}^\ddagger$) of Lewis acid and base^{6, 15}. $\Delta E_{nm}^\ddagger$ values have been calculated for Mo-L and Fe-L interactions (Table 2). Higher values are obtained for Mo-L interactions in comparison to Fe-L interactions, supporting the attachment of ligands to Mo^{III}.

Biological activity Antifungal activity of the complexes was evaluated in the agar medium at pH 6–7 against soil fungi like *Aspergillus sydowi* and *A. flavus*. The growth inhibition percentage was calculated on the basis of average diameter of the fungal colonies. Complete disappearance of fungal colonies was noticed in the test plate giving 100% inhibition of both the fungi compared with the control. These complexes may be recommended as antifungal agents.

TABLE 2 - MATCHING OF THE LIGANDS WITH MO^{III} AND Fe^{II}

Compd	$E_m^\ddagger$	$\Delta E_{nm}^\ddagger$ (Mo-L)	$\Delta E_{nm}^\ddagger$ (Fe-L)
Pyridine	11.06	12.01	11.39
Nicotinamide	13.72	14.67	14.05
2,2'-Bipyridyl	11.70	12.65	12.03
1,10-Phenanthroline	11.98	12.93	12.31

$F_n^\ddagger$ Mo^{III} = 0.93, $F_n^\ddagger$ Fe^{II} = 0.33

Calculation of softness values of metal ions and ligands refers to methanol medium.

Experimental

Reagent grade solvents were used after purification by standard methods. Pyridine (Glauc), nicotinamide (Loba), 2,2'-bipyridyl (B D H), 1,10-phenanthroline (E Merck), ammonium heptamolybdate (Loba), ferrous sulphate (Ranbaxy) and potassium thiocyanate (B D H) were used as such. K₃MoCl₆ was prepared by the reported method¹⁶.

K[Fe(NCS)₆][Mo(py)₆] and K[Fe(NCS)₆][Mo(mia)₆] To the suspension of K₃MoCl₆ (0.426 g, 1 mmol) in methanol (20 ml) suspension of ferrous sulphate (0.152 g, 1 mmol) in methanol (20 ml) and potassium thiocyanate (0.582 g, 6 mmol) in methanol (15 ml) were added and the mixture was stirred for 24 h at room temperature. The white precipitate of potassium chloride and potassium sulphate formed was discarded and to the filtrate was added pyridine (0.48 ml, 6 mmol) and stirred for 24 h at room temperature. The resulting solid was washed with sol-

vent and dried in under reduced pressure to yield $K[Fe(NCS)_6][Mo(py)_6]$.

The $K[Fe(NCS)_6][Mo(nia)_6]$ was similarly prepared by using methanolic suspension of nicotinamide instead of pyridine.

$K[Fe(NCS)_6][Mo(bipy)_3]$ and $K[Fe(NCS)_6][Mo(phen)_3]$: To a suspension of K_3MoCl_6 (0.426 g, 1 mmol) in methanol (20 ml) suspensions of ferrous sulphate (0.152 g, 1 mmol) in methanol (20 ml) and potassium thiocyanate (0.582 g, 6 mmol) in methanol (15 ml) were added and the mixture was stirred for 24 h at room temperature. The white precipitate of potassium sulphate formed was discarded, and to the filtrate bipyridyl (0.468 g, 3 mmol) dissolved in methanol (10 ml) was added and further stirred for 24 h. The resulting solid was washed with solvent and dried under reduced pressure to yield $K[Fe(NCS)_6][Mo(bipy)_3]$.

$K[Fe(NCS)_6][Mo(phen)_3]$ was similarly prepared by using methanolic suspension of 1,10-phenanthroline in place of 2,2'-bipyridyl.

Molybdenum was estimated as lead molybdate, iron as ferric oxide and sulphur as barium sulphate by standard methods¹⁷. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method.

Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (nujol) on a Carry-14 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on Gouy balance using $CoHg(SCN)_4$ as standard. Molar conductance of the complexes were determined in DMF at 0.001 M dilution using an Elico CM 82T conductivity bridge.

Activity of compounds on soil fungi was tested using 0.01 M aqueous suspension (1 ml) in each dish containing 1 ml of soil suspension (0.1 mg) by dilution plate method¹⁸ on molten Czapek's media (15 ml). A control experiment was also made. All dishes were covered and left for 48 h at room temperature (25–38°). Pepton beef extract agar medium (15 ml) was used and pH adjusted at about 7. The percentage inhibition was calculated as described earlier¹⁹.

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